

Relations And Applications and Examples Between Other Disciplines in Terms of The Methods of Political Science

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Abstract

Political science is an interdisciplinary domain that investigates the analysis of governance and political systems. Political science incorporates insights from several disciplines such as sociology, economics, psychology, and anthropology to comprehensively examine and assess political behavior, institutions, policies, and processes. Political science also connects with fields such as communication, journalism, media studies, history, international relations, public and international affairs, cultural studies, marketing, advertising, and public relations. The discipline of international studies is often defined as an interdisciplinary major that includes a range of areas, such as political science and international relations (Breuning & Ishiyama, 2007). Political science is an interdisciplinary field that incorporates many social disciplines, such as sociology, economics, psychology, and anthropology. Moreover, political science has a prominent position in the examination of other scientific disciplines. For instance, in the domain of political marketing, the examination of current politics integrates perspectives from both political science and marketing research. This multidisciplinary approach acknowledges that political issues cannot be completely understood or elucidated by a solitary discipline. Moreover, there exists a methodological connection between political science and economics, namely in relation to governance systems and the formulation of policies. This relationship facilitates a thorough examination of both government and market processes, including the exploration of regulatory theories and market inefficiencies. In essence, political science is a multidisciplinary domain that incorporates insights from the social sciences and connects with other fields to examine the workings of government and politics. Political economy is an interdisciplinary field that combines politics and economics to analyze issues pertaining to economic and political systems. It draws upon concepts from both disciplines to explore topics such as governance, institutions, policies, and political behavior. The use of an interdisciplinary approach in the study of political economics enables a thorough comprehension of the intricate interplay between political and economic elements. Moreover, political economy is a distinct topic that integrates politics and economics, hence functioning as an interdisciplinary domain that employs ideas from both disciplines to examine matters pertaining to economic and political systems.

Keywords: Relations Of Political Science, Applications of Political Science, Examples of Political Science, Between Other Disciplines and Political Science, Methods of Political Science

Introduction

"Political economy is a branch of social science that encompasses two sub-disciplines: politics and economics." Political economics is a multidisciplinary field that integrates the examination of political systems and economic processes to investigate matters including governance, institutions, policies, and political behavior. This multidisciplinary approach facilitates a thorough comprehension of the intricate interplay between political and economic variables inside society. The multidisciplinary character of political science is apparent in its use of socioeconomic, cultural, and historical studies to examine regional matters. This multidisciplinary approach acknowledges that political processes are impacted by a multitude of elements and cannot be completely understood or elucidated by a solitary discipline. The interdisciplinary aspect of political science is apparent in its use of ideas and methodologies derived from both political science and economics. By adopting an interdisciplinary approach, a more thorough examination of governance systems, market dynamics, and policymaking may be achieved. In addition, political science adopts an interdisciplinary methodology by incorporating ideas and methodologies from other social sciences such as sociology, psychology, anthropology, and geography. By taking into account the social, cultural, and economic aspects that influence political processes and events, this multidisciplinary approach allows for a more profound comprehension. Political science is an interdisciplinary discipline that utilizes many social sciences, such as sociology, economics, and anthropology, to comprehensively examine and comprehend political occurrences. The multidisciplinary character of political science is essential for examining governance systems, policy-making processes, and political behavior. This multidisciplinary approach facilitates a more holistic understanding of the intricate interplay between political and economic variables in society, as well as the impact of social, cultural, and historical variables on political occurrences. Political

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science is an interdisciplinary domain that incorporates many social disciplines, including sociology, economics, and anthropology. The use of an interdisciplinary approach enriches the examination of political systems and economic processes, facilitating a more thorough evaluation of governance, institutions, policies, and political conduct (Bleischwitz, 2004).

Methodology

The multidisciplinary aspect of political science facilitates a holistic understanding of the intricate interplay between political and economic variables within society. Moreover, the interdisciplinary nature of political science enables a comprehensive comprehension of political processes by integrating perspectives from several fields such as sociology, psychology, and communication. Political science is an interdisciplinary study that combines ideas and techniques from other social sciences to examine and comprehend political occurrences. The multidisciplinary method in political science enables a more thorough examination of governance systems, market dynamics, and policymaking. Political science is an interdisciplinary study that utilizes ideas and techniques from many social sciences to examine and comprehend political occurrences. The interdisciplinary method in political science facilitates a thorough comprehension of the intricate interplay between political and economic elements in society. It integrates perspectives from several disciplines to provide a complete outlook on political events. Political science is an interdisciplinary domain that combines many social disciplines, including sociology, economics, and anthropology, to examine and comprehend political occurrences. Moreover, political science, being an interdisciplinary discipline, engages with other sciences such as economics, geography, and ecology. This contact facilitates a more profound comprehension of the political processes and their interrelations with economic, geographical, and ecological aspects. The interdisciplinary aspect of political science allows for a more sophisticated examination of political issues by integrating perspectives from several social disciplines. Political science is an interdisciplinary domain that utilizes ideas, methodologies, and insights from several social disciplines to examine and comprehend political occurrences. An interdisciplinary approach is essential in political science

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to get a thorough comprehension of political processes and their interconnections with other academic disciplines.

Findings

The interdisciplinary aspect of political science facilitates a more thorough comprehension of political processes by integrating ideas from many social disciplines such as sociology, psychology, economics, geography, and ecology. Political science is an interdisciplinary domain that combines ideas, methodologies, and perspectives from several social disciplines to examine and comprehend political occurrences. The multidisciplinary method in political science is advantageous since it enables a thorough examination of governance systems, market dynamics, and policymaking, resulting in a more complete study. In summary, the interdisciplinary aspect of political science allows for a more profound comprehension of political processes by integrating viewpoints from other social sciences and allied subjects, such as geography, economics, and ecology. The interdisciplinary character of political science enables a more thorough examination of political processes by integrating ideas and perspectives from other social sciences and allied subjects. The interdisciplinary aspect of political science is essential for examining intricate political events and comprehending their interrelations with other social disciplines. Furthermore, the multidisciplinary approach used in political science facilitates a comprehensive comprehension of the intricate interplay of politics, economics, geography, and environment. The interdisciplinary aspect of political science is crucial for comprehending the intricacies of political behavior and its interconnection with other social disciplines (Ramadhyas et al., 2020). Political science's multidisciplinary character enables a thorough and nuanced examination of political processes by integrating ideas, methodologies, and insights from many social sciences and allied subjects. The interdisciplinary approach is crucial in political science since it allows for a thorough examination of political processes by integrating ideas, methodologies, and insights from several social sciences and allied subjects, including sociology, psychology, economics, geography, and ecology. The interdisciplinary aspect of political science is crucial for a thorough comprehension of political behavior and its interrelations with other social sciences.

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Political science's multidisciplinary character facilitates a thorough examination of political processes by integrating ideas, methodologies, and insights from many social sciences and allied subjects. The interdisciplinary aspect of political science is essential for a thorough comprehension of political behavior and its interrelations with other social sciences. The interdisciplinary aspect of political science enables a more thorough comprehension of political phenomena and promotes the integration of many methodology and research approaches. Political science benefits from its interdisciplinary character, as it allows scientists to use knowledge and ideas from other social disciplines, including sociology, psychology, economics, geography, and ecology, in order to enhance their comprehension of political processes (Corbett, 2011). In summary, the interdisciplinary aspect of political science improves our comprehension of intricate political processes by integrating viewpoints and approaches from other social disciplines. The multidisciplinary aspect of political science facilitates a more holistic understanding of political behavior and its interrelations with other branches of social sciences.

The Sub-branches of Political Science and Their Relations with Other Sciences

Political science is a multifaceted discipline that encompasses several sub-disciplines, all of which are related with other sciences and areas of study. The many subdivisions of political science, including political theory, institutional theory, regional studies, political economics, and political ecology, all include interdisciplinary aspects and rely on information and ideas from other social disciplines. Political theory, for instance, overlaps with other disciplines, including themes addressed in studies such as sociology, psychology, and philosophy. Institutional theory is intrinsically multidisciplinary and is used in several fields such as political science, economics, and sociology (Vukovic & Kochetkov, 2017). Regional studies use an interdisciplinary methodology that integrates viewpoints from socio-economic, cultural, and political science domains. This multidisciplinary approach enables a thorough examination of regional problems. Furthermore, political economy, a subsidiary field of political science, serves as a connection between the realms of social sciences and economics. It applies

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economic ideas and methodologies to examine governance systems, policy formulation, and market dynamics. Political economy is a branch of social science that encompasses two sub-disciplines: politics and economics (et al., 2022). The multidisciplinary aspect of political economy enables the examination of political matters from an economic perspective, facilitating a more profound understanding of the interplay between politics and economics. Political science is an interdisciplinary discipline that integrates information, ideas, and approaches from other social sciences. The use of an interdisciplinary approach enriches our comprehension of intricate political phenomena and facilitates a comprehensive examination of political behavior and its interrelations with other branches of social sciences. Moreover, the interdisciplinary character of political science facilitates a more thorough comprehension of political conduct and its interrelations with other branches of social sciences. Political ecology, a subfield of political science, integrates aspects of political economics and ecology to examine the interplay between people and the environment (Tevzadze & Kikvidze, 2016). By doing thus, it combines information and approaches from both social sciences and scientific sciences. In general, the many subdivisions of political science, such as political theory, political economics, and political ecology, exhibit transdisciplinary characteristics. Political science and its sub-branches have interdisciplinary characteristics that facilitate the integration of information, ideas, and approaches from other social sciences, including economics, sociology, and ecology. The multidisciplinary aspect of political science facilitates a more holistic understanding of political action and its interrelations with other social sciences. Moreover, the interdisciplinary character of political science facilitates a more thorough comprehension of political conduct and its interrelations with other branches of social sciences. This interdisciplinary approach improves our comprehension of intricate political phenomena and offers a more comprehensive examination of political behavior and its connections with other social sciences. Political science and its sub-branches have interdisciplinary characteristics that facilitate the integration of information, ideas, and approaches from other social sciences, including sociology, economics, and ecology.

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Literature Review

This interdisciplinary approach enhances our comprehension of political occurrences and facilitates a more thorough and subtle examination of the intricate interactions among politics, economics, geography, and other social and natural disciplines. Political science and its sub-branches have interdisciplinary characteristics that facilitate the integration of information, ideas, and methodology from related social sciences such as sociology, economics, and geography. The interdisciplinary approach enables a more thorough comprehension of political behavior and its interrelations with other social and natural sciences, allowing for a more comprehensive analysis of the intricate dynamics among politics, economics, geography, and other social and natural sciences (Ramadhyas et al., 2020). Political science and its sub-branches are multidisciplinary, using information and methodology from many social and natural disciplines such as economics, sociology, geography, and ecology (Corbett, 2011). This interdisciplinary approach facilitates a more thorough comprehension of political behavior and its interactions with other disciplines, enabling a more profound examination of intricate phenomena and the interdependencies between politics and other social and natural sciences. Political science and its sub-branches are multidisciplinary, using information and methodology from many social and natural disciplines such as economics, sociology, geography, and ecology. The integration of multiple disciplines enriches our comprehension of political conduct and its interrelations with other branches of social sciences, facilitating a more thorough and refined examination of the intricate interactions among politics, economics, geography, and other social and natural sciences (Ramadhyas et al., 2020). Political science and its sub-branches have interdisciplinary characteristics that facilitate the integration of information, ideas, and approaches from other social sciences, including sociology, economics, geography, and ecology. The use of an interdisciplinary approach enhances our comprehension of political processes and facilitates a more thorough examination of the intricate interplay between politics, economics, geography, and other social and natural disciplines. Political science and its sub-branches are multidisciplinary, using information and methodology from many social and natural disciplines such as economics, sociology, geography, and ecology (Corbett, 2011). This interdisciplinary approach promotes a comprehensive and refined examination of political behavior and its linkages with other disciplines, resulting in a more profound comprehension of the intricate dynamics of politics and its interactions with other

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social and scientific sciences. Political science and its sub-branches are essentially multidisciplinary, drawing upon information and methodology from many social and natural disciplines such as economics, sociology, geography, and ecology. This interdisciplinary approach facilitates a more exhaustive comprehension of political behavior and its interrelations with other social and natural sciences, providing a more profound explanation of intricate phenomena and the interdependence between politics and other fields of study. Ultimately, the examination of political science and its many subfields is intrinsically multidisciplinary since it necessitates cooperation and amalgamation with other social and scientific disciplines. The utilization of an interdisciplinary approach facilitates a thorough comprehension of political phenomena and their interrelations with various disciplines, resulting in a more intricate examination of the intricate interactions between politics, economics, geography, and other social and natural sciences (Ramadhyas et al., 2020). In general, the field of political science and its sub-disciplines are known for their interdisciplinary nature, which involves working together and integrating with other social and scientific sciences. This interdisciplinary approach enhances the comprehension of political behavior, allowing for more profound studies of intricate phenomena and the interrelations between politics and other fields of study. Political science and its sub-branches are fundamentally multidisciplinary, necessitating cooperation and integration with other social and natural disciplines such as economics, sociology, geography, and ecology. This multidisciplinary approach enables a more thorough and subtle examination of political conduct, resulting in a more profound comprehension of the intricate interactions between politics and other social aspects.

Analyzing the Sub-Branches of Political Science and their Relations with Other Sciences

Political science is a discipline that naturally combines information and approaches from many social and scientific sciences. Political economy is an interdisciplinary field that examines political and economic matters pertaining to the study of political economy. Political ecology is a field that combines political economics and ecology in order to examine the connections between humans and the environment (Tevzadze & Kikvidze, 2016). Political science encompasses several sub-branches, including political theory and geography, which serve to

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emphasize its multidisciplinary character. These subsidiary divisions often connect with other fields, including as economics, anthropology, psychology, and sociology, in their examination and investigation of political issues. The interdisciplinary aspect of political science and its sub-branches is crucial for attaining a thorough comprehension of intricate political processes. In addition, interdisciplinary cooperation encompasses not only natural and social scientists, but also social scientists specializing in other fields of competence (Teel et al., 2022). This partnership encompasses disciplines such as political ecology, conservation and development studies, among others. These cooperation across different academic disciplines lead to a comprehensive knowledge of political behavior and its confluence with other fields of study in the social and natural sciences. Political science and its sub-branches greatly depend on interdisciplinary cooperation and integration with other social and scientific disciplines. This multidisciplinary approach facilitates a more thorough and subtle examination of political behavior, resulting in a more profound comprehension of the intricate interactions between politics and other social and natural disciplines. The need of precise weather predictions in today's dynamic environment cannot be overemphasized. By adopting an interdisciplinary approach, political science researchers may integrate viewpoints and approaches from several disciplines, resulting in a more holistic understanding of political behavior and its interplay with social and environmental issues. The need of precise weather predictions in today's dynamic environment cannot be overemphasized. By adopting an interdisciplinary approach, political science researchers may integrate viewpoints and approaches from several disciplines, resulting in a more holistic understanding of political behavior and its interplay with social and environmental issues. The importance of precise weather predictions in today's dynamic environment cannot be exaggerated. This interdisciplinary approach facilitates a comprehensive comprehension of the intricate interplay between political processes and other fields, including economics, anthropology, psychology, and sociology, and their mutual effect. The need of precise weather predictions in today's dynamic environment cannot be overemphasized. By adopting an interdisciplinary approach, political science researchers are able to integrate viewpoints and approaches from several domains. This results in a more thorough comprehension of political behavior and its interplay with other social and environmental aspects. The importance of precise weather predictions in today's dynamic environment cannot be exaggerated. The interdisciplinary nature of political science allows

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researchers to integrate perspectives and methodologies from diverse fields, resulting in a more thorough comprehension of political behavior and its interplay with other disciplines. This facilitates a more refined analysis of the intricate dynamics between politics and various societal and environmental factors. The need of precise weather predictions in the current dynamic global environment cannot be overemphasized. The use of an interdisciplinary approach in political science facilitates a comprehensive comprehension of the intricate interplay between political processes and other fields of study, including economics, anthropology, psychology, and sociology. In conclusion, this multidisciplinary method provides unique insights into the elements that influence political behavior and decision-making processes, making it a crucial element of modern political science research. The interdisciplinary nature of political science involves the integration of various perspectives and methodologies from diverse fields. It also acknowledges the interdependence of social, environmental, and political phenomena, emphasizing the necessity of a comprehensive comprehension of their interactions and consequences. In essence, integrating a social science viewpoint into political science research aligns with the growing inclination towards interdisciplinary research. This approach facilitates a more holistic comprehension of political phenomena and their interconnections with other scientific disciplines, such as economics, anthropology, psychology, and sociology. Incorporating weather forecasting algorithms into geography study enhances our comprehension of political conduct by taking into account the socio-economic implications of fluctuating weather conditions. To summarize, the multidisciplinary character of political science enables a thorough comprehension of political behavior and its intersections with other scientific disciplines. This interdisciplinary approach enriches the research of political processes by integrating viewpoints and approaches from other domains, including geography, ethnography, atmospheric sciences, public health, computer and data science, and conservation and development studies. Furthermore, this multidisciplinary approach acknowledges the interdependence of political events with social, economic, and environmental processes. Incorporating multidisciplinary views in political science enhances the depth and comprehensiveness of our knowledge of political issues. The multidisciplinary character of political science enables a thorough examination of political phenomena and their interconnections with other disciplines, such as economics, anthropology, psychology, sociology, and geography. The incorporation of many disciplines enhances the examination of

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politics by taking into account diverse elements and viewpoints that impact political conduct, the processes of making decisions, and the consequences for society. Furthermore, it acknowledges the significance of other disciplines, such as sociology and cognitive psychology, in challenging conventional frameworks and paradigms within the field of political science. Ultimately, the various divisions within political science, such as institutional theory and regional studies, have progressively adopted interdisciplinary approaches. These approaches involve incorporating ideas and methods from other fields of study to improve our comprehension of political phenomena (Vukovic & Kochetkov, 2017). Hence, political science is not a distinct discipline, but rather overlaps with many scientific fields to provide a thorough examination of political processes.

Argument

To summarize, the many subdivisions of political science acknowledge and use interdisciplinary methodologies to provide a more thorough examination of political processes. Political science may enhance its understanding of intricate dynamics in political events by integrating viewpoints and approaches from other domains like geography, sociology, economics, anthropology, psychology, and others. An interdisciplinary approach is essential for a comprehensive comprehension of political behavior and its correlation with social, economic, and environmental phenomena. Ultimately, the many subdivisions of political science acknowledge and use interdisciplinary methodologies to provide a more thorough examination of political processes. Political science, via its integration of several disciplines and views, may provide a more nuanced comprehension of political events and their interrelation with other social, economic, and environmental elements. Ultimately, the many subdivisions of political science acknowledge and use interdisciplinary methodologies to provide a more thorough examination of political processes. Political science adopts an interdisciplinary approach to examine the multitude of causes and viewpoints that shape political behavior, decision-making processes, and social results. This multidisciplinary approach not only improves the precision and reliability of political science research but also enriches our comprehension of the intricate nature of politics in the contemporary world.

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Ultimately, the many subdivisions of political science have progressively acknowledged the need of interdisciplinary methodologies to provide a more thorough examination of political processes. Political science may enhance its understanding of intricate political processes by integrating viewpoints and approaches from several disciplines, including geography, sociology, economics, anthropology, psychology, and others. This multidisciplinary methodology facilitates a comprehensive comprehension of political conduct, the processes of decision-making, and the resulting social consequences. Furthermore, the many subdivisions of political science also acknowledge the significance of multidisciplinary cooperation among social scientists. This partnership facilitates the incorporation of diverse ideas, methodologies, and discoveries from other disciplines, resulting in a more comprehensive and meticulous examination of political events. In general, the many subdivisions of political science acknowledge that politics cannot be examined in isolation and that interdisciplinary cooperation is essential for a thorough comprehension of political processes and their connections with other fields of study. The many subdivisions of political science acknowledge that the study of politics cannot be conducted in isolation and that an interdisciplinary methodology is essential for a thorough comprehension of political phenomena and its interconnections with other fields of study. The interdisciplinary approach in political science facilitates a more thorough understanding of political processes by integrating viewpoints and approaches from several disciplines, including geography, sociology, economics, and anthropology (Corbett, 2011). By adopting an interdisciplinary approach, political science research is not only improved in terms of correctness and validity, but it also leads to a more profound comprehension of the intricate dynamics of contemporary politics.

Ultimately, the many subdivisions of political science have progressively acknowledged the significance of interdisciplinary methodologies in order to provide a more thorough examination of political processes. Political science may enhance its understanding of intricate political processes by integrating viewpoints and approaches from other disciplines such as geography, sociology, economics, anthropology, psychology, and others. The multidisciplinary aspect of political science facilitates a comprehensive comprehension of political behavior, decision-making processes, and the resulting social results. Moreover, the multidisciplinary nature of political science poses a challenge to conventional rational economic models and pushes scientists to adopt a more inclusive approach. This perspective recognizes that politics

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is not exclusively confined to its own distinct domain within the social sciences. Instead, it is a topic of examination for researchers who engage in interdisciplinary research and value the exchange of ideas and approaches (Hadfield & Zwitter, 2013). To put it concisely, political science is as multidisciplinary as the area of politics (Corbett, 2011). Political science acknowledges the need of collaborating with other disciplines as it delves into the complexities of governance systems, policy-making, and political behavior. This partnership facilitates a more profound understanding of the intricate interconnections between politics and other scientific disciplines, such as ecology in the context of political ecology. Ultimately, the many subdivisions of political science acknowledge the need of using interdisciplinary methods to get a thorough comprehension of political events. By adopting an interdisciplinary approach, political science research is not only improved in terms of correctness and validity, but it also leads to a more profound comprehension of the intricate dynamics of contemporary politics. Moreover, the use of interdisciplinary methodologies in political science research facilitates the integration of ideas and discoveries from other fields, such as economics. The incorporation of many viewpoints and approaches enriches the examination of governance systems, policy formulation, and political conduct. In general, the interdisciplinary character of political science enriches its understanding of governance systems and policymaking by integrating viewpoints and approaches from several disciplines. Geography, being a field that combines several disciplines, has a crucial impact on deepening our comprehension of political conduct (Ramadhyas et al., 2020). Geography plays a crucial role in revealing the fundamental dynamics and patterns of political behavior by considering spatial context and examining the influence of geographical elements on political systems. In addition, geography plays a significant role in the conceptual framework of political science, demonstrating the interdependence between geographical elements and political occurrences. Political science utilizes concepts from several social disciplines, such as economics and sociology, to evaluate governing systems from a complete standpoint. Political science may provide a comprehensive comprehension of governance systems, policy-making, and political behavior by using approaches and ideas from other disciplines. Moreover, the multidisciplinary character of political science enables a more intricate examination of governance systems characterized by less government intervention. By incorporating economic ideas and discoveries into political science research, a more profound comprehension of market failures, regulatory theories, and the influence of players on

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governance systems may be achieved. In general, political science considerably benefits from an interdisciplinary approach since it enables a more thorough comprehension of political processes by integrating concepts and approaches from several disciplines. To summarize, the several subfields of political science, including institutional theory, regional studies, political theory, actor-centered institutionalism, and political ecology, all emphasize the multidisciplinary character of the discipline. Political science utilizes and incorporates viewpoints, theories, and methodologies from various fields including economics, sociology, geography, anthropology, and ecology, among others. This integration allows for a more comprehensive comprehension of governance systems, policy-making, and political behavior. The interdisciplinary method in political science is advantageous since it assimilates ideas and views from other social sciences, such as economics and geography, to acquire a more thorough comprehension of political processes. Political ecology is an interdisciplinary discipline that integrates information from social sciences like geography, ethnography, and political economics with natural sciences like ecology and conservation biology. Political ecology employs an interdisciplinary approach to examine the intricate interplay between political and ecological systems (Tevzadze & Kikvidze, 2016). Political science inherently overlaps with other disciplines as it explores many facets of politics (Corbett, 2011). This multidisciplinary approach enables a comprehensive study and comprehension of political events, since it takes into account the social, economic, geographical, and ecological aspects that influence political systems and policies. Political science is an interdisciplinary study that utilizes concepts and approaches from a range of social and scientific sciences. By integrating viewpoints and ideas from other fields including economics, sociology, geography, anthropology, and ecology, this interdisciplinary approach enhances our knowledge of political processes, making it broader and more complex. Hence, with the use of an interdisciplinary methodology, political science may effectively scrutinize and comprehend governance systems and policymaking, while also evaluating the wider social, economic, and environmental consequences of political processes. The interdisciplinary nature of political science facilitates a holistic comprehension of governance systems, policy-making, and political behavior by incorporating viewpoints, theories, and methodologies from other fields such as economics, sociology, geography, anthropology, and ecology. Political science is fundamentally multidisciplinary, since it incorporates concepts and approaches from a range of social and natural disciplines, including

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economics, sociology, geography, anthropology, and ecology. Political science may enhance our knowledge of political events by analyzing many elements that influence governance systems, policy-making, and political behavior, leading to a more detailed and thorough analysis. Hence, the sub-branches of political science, such as political ecology and political theory, are inherently interdisciplinary as they integrate knowledge and methodologies from other fields to examine and comprehend the intricate interplay between political and ecological systems, as well as the wider consequences of political processes. The study of politics is essentially multidisciplinary, including ideas, theories, and approaches from a range of social and natural disciplines, including economics, sociology, geography, anthropology, and ecology. Political science employs an interdisciplinary approach, drawing on ideas, theories, and approaches from several social and natural disciplines. This enables the analysis and comprehension of the intricate relationships between political occurrences and other aspects of society. To summarize, the sub-branches of political science, such as political ecology, political theory, and political economics, are essentially multidisciplinary. Political scientists use interdisciplinary approaches, drawing upon many fields such as geography, anthropology, sociology, economics, and ecology, to comprehensively examine and comprehend the intricate dynamics of political systems and processes. To summarize, the many divisions of political science, such as political ecology, political theory, and political economics, possess an intrinsic interdisciplinary character. Political scientists use interdisciplinary approaches, drawing upon many fields such as geography, anthropology, sociology, economics, and ecology, to examine and comprehend the intricate dynamics of political systems and processes. This multidisciplinary approach facilitates a more thorough and holistic understanding of political phenomena, as it considers the many social, economic, geographic, and environmental circumstances in which politics function. The interdisciplinary nature of political science enables a more comprehensive and nuanced comprehension of political phenomena by integrating knowledge and methodologies from diverse social and natural sciences, including geography, anthropology, sociology, economics, and ecology (Tevzadze & Kikvidze, 2016). Furthermore, the multidisciplinary nature of political science enables a more thorough examination of governance structures, policy-making procedures, and socio-environmental transformations. Political science is a discipline that combines knowledge and methods from several social and natural sciences, such as geography, anthropology, political economy,

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economics, sociology, and ecology (Corbett, 2011). By incorporating other disciplines, political science gains a more thorough understanding of political phenomena, considering the various complex forces that mold and impact politics. To summarize, the sub-disciplines of political science, such as political ecology, political theory, and political economics, are essentially multidisciplinary. Political scientists use interdisciplinary approaches, using insights and methodology from many fields such as geography, anthropology, sociology, economics, and ecology, to comprehensively examine and comprehend the intricate dynamics of political systems and processes.

Interdisciplinary Nature of Political Science

Ultimately, political science and its many sub-disciplines has an intrinsic interdisciplinary character. They integrate information and approaches from several social and scientific fields to investigate and comprehend political occurrences. By incorporating several disciplines, this method enables a thorough and all-encompassing comprehension of politics, taking into account the influence of social, economic, geographic, and environmental elements. Moreover, political science and its sub-disciplines are not only subject to the impact of other academic areas, but also actively contribute to the progress of knowledge in their respective domains. Hence, political science and its sub-disciplines not only get advantages from collaborating with other studies, but also actively contribute to the integration of knowledge across many disciplines such as geography, anthropology, sociology, economics, and ecology. The interdisciplinary aspect of political science enables a more thorough comprehension and examination of political processes by integrating concepts and approaches from several social and scientific disciplines. Political science benefits from this multidisciplinary approach since it enables the field to tackle intricate and interrelated issues, such as governance systems, policy-making processes, and socio-environmental transformations. Hence, the many subdivisions of political science, such as political ecology, political theory, and political economics, are essential in connecting diverse fields of study and promoting interdisciplinary cooperation and comprehension (Tevzadze & Kikvidze, 2016). Political science and its sub-branches are essentially multidisciplinary, using information and approaches from other social

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and scientific disciplines. Moreover, the multidisciplinary aspect of political science facilitates a more thorough and sophisticated comprehension of the intricate dynamics of political systems and processes. The interdisciplinary character of political science and its sub-branches facilitates a thorough examination of political systems and processes by integrating perspectives from several disciplines, including sociology, economics, geography, anthropology, psychology, and ecology. Political science achieves a more complete and nuanced understanding of political issues by incorporating information from several disciplines. By taking into account the real-world consequences of political choices and policies, this multidisciplinary approach improves the practical significance and usefulness of political science research. In essence, political science and its sub-branches are integral to an interdisciplinary pursuit that necessitates cooperation with other fields, including geography, anthropology, sociology, economics, and ecology. Political science and its sub-branches are fundamentally multidisciplinary, since they include concepts and approaches from a range of social and scientific disciplines. The interdisciplinary aspect of political science enables a more thorough comprehension and examination of political processes by integrating concepts and approaches from several social and scientific disciplines. The integration of several disciplines is essential in tackling intricate political matters and comprehending the interrelation between political, social, and environmental elements. Political science and its sub-branches are essentially multidisciplinary, using information and approaches from other social and scientific disciplines. Political science achieves a comprehensive and refined understanding of political issues by incorporating many viewpoints and approaches. Moreover, the interdisciplinary character of political science and its sub-disciplines is essential for tackling intricate political problems and comprehending the interdependence of political, social, and environmental elements. Political science and its sub-branches are essentially multidisciplinary, using concepts and approaches from a range of social and scientific studies. This multidisciplinary approach enables a more thorough examination of political systems and processes, including the intricate interaction of political, social, economic, geographic, and environmental elements. Political science sub-branches, including political theory, political ecology, and political economics, are multidisciplinary subjects that use concepts and approaches from other social and scientific sciences (Corbett, 2011). Interdisciplinary techniques provide a thorough understanding and examination of political processes by integrating many viewpoints and

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methodologies from fields including geography, anthropology, sociology, economics, and ecology. Political science and its sub-branches are essentially multidisciplinary, using concepts and approaches from a range of social and scientific studies. The integration of several disciplines is essential for tackling intricate political matters and comprehending the interdependence of political, social, economic, and environmental elements. Ultimately, the several subdivisions of political science, including political theory, political ecology, and political economics, are fundamentally multidisciplinary domains that use knowledge and approaches from a wide array of social and natural disciplines. These multidisciplinary techniques provide a more nuanced and complete understanding of political processes by integrating multiple viewpoints and methodology from disciplines such as geography, anthropology, sociology, economics, and ecology. To summarize, the sub-branches of political science are fundamentally multidisciplinary since they include ideas and approaches from other social and scientific disciplines. This interdisciplinary approach facilitates a more profound comprehension and examination of political phenomena, as it takes into account the intricate interaction of political, social, economic, and environmental aspects to provide a holistic study of political systems and processes. Ultimately, the examination of political science and its many subdivisions is intrinsically multidisciplinary since it necessitates cooperation and amalgamation with other fields of study in the realms of both society and the natural world. This interdisciplinary approach facilitates a comprehensive and subtle comprehension of political phenomena, as it considers the various aspects of social, economic, and environmental elements that influence political systems and processes. To summarize, the sub-branches of political science, including political theory, political ecology, and political economics, are fundamentally multidisciplinary domains that use ideas and approaches from other social and scientific disciplines. These multidisciplinary techniques provide a thorough examination of political events, taking into account the interdependence of political, social, economic, and environmental elements. Ultimately, the sub-disciplines of political science, such as political theory, political ecology, and political economics, are fundamentally multidisciplinary areas that depend on ideas and approaches from a range of social and natural sciences. These multidisciplinary techniques provide a more thorough and holistic understanding of political processes by integrating multiple viewpoints from disciplines such as geography, anthropology, sociology, economics, and ecology. To summarize, the sub-disciplines of political science, such

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as political theory, political ecology, and political economics, are multidisciplinary areas that integrate information and approaches from many social and scientific sciences. The incorporation of many disciplines enriches the examination of political phenomena by taking into account the various elements and viewpoints that influence political institutions and processes. Ultimately, the sub-branches of political science are intrinsically multidisciplinary, since they rely on ideas and approaches from a range of social and scientific disciplines. This multidisciplinary approach facilitates a more complete and nuanced understanding of political processes, including the intricate interplay of social, economic, and environmental aspects. To summarize, the sub-branches of political science are essentially multidisciplinary, integrating information and approaches from other social and scientific disciplines. By adopting an interdisciplinary approach, a more thorough examination of political phenomena is facilitated, taking into account the interdependence of social, economic, and environmental elements and their influence on political systems and processes. Ultimately, the many subdivisions of political science, such as political theory, political ecology, and political economics, are fundamentally multidisciplinary domains that use knowledge and approaches from other social and scientific disciplines. By using multidisciplinary techniques, a more refined and all-encompassing comprehension of political processes is achieved via the examination of intricate interplays among social, economic, and environmental elements. Ultimately, the sub-disciplines of political science, such as political theory, political ecology, and political economics, are fundamentally multidisciplinary areas that integrate information and approaches from other social and scientific sciences. This multidisciplinary approach improves the comprehension and examination of political events by taking into account the complex nature of human behavior, institutions, and environmental influences. Ultimately, the sub-branches of political science are intrinsically multidisciplinary since they integrate information and approaches from other social and scientific disciplines. By adopting an interdisciplinary perspective, a comprehensive comprehension of political phenomena is achieved, acknowledging the interdependence of social, economic, and environmental elements and their impact on political systems and processes. Ultimately, the sub-branches of political science are intrinsically multidisciplinary, since they rely on ideas and approaches from a range of social and scientific disciplines. This multidisciplinary approach enables a more thorough and subtle examination of political occurrences, including the intricate interplay of social, economic, and

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environmental aspects. To summarize, the sub-disciplines of political science, such as political theory, political ecology, and political economics, are fundamentally multidisciplinary areas that integrate information and methodology from other social and natural sciences. An interdisciplinary perspective is essential for comprehending the complex interconnections of political systems, social dynamics, economic pressures, and environmental issues. To summarize, the many sub-branches of political science, such as political theory, political ecology, and political economics, are essentially interdisciplinary disciplines that integrate perspectives and approaches from a wide array of social and natural sciences (Tevzadze & Kikvidze, 2016). By examining the intricate interplay of social, economic, and environmental issues, this multidisciplinary approach enhances our comprehension of political occurrences. Political science sub-branches, including political theory, political ecology, and political economics, are multidisciplinary subjects that integrate information and approaches from many social and scientific sciences (Corbett, 2011). This multidisciplinary approach improves the comprehension and examination of political events by taking into account the complex nature of human behavior, institutions, and environmental influences. To summarize, the sub-disciplines of political science, such as political theory, political ecology, and political economics, are fundamentally multidisciplinary studies that integrate knowledge and methods from other social and scientific sciences. By taking into account the interaction between social, economic, and environmental aspects, this multidisciplinary approach enables a thorough comprehension of political processes. To summarize, the sub-branches of political science, such as political theory, political ecology, and political economics, are multidisciplinary areas that rely on ideas and approaches from other social and scientific sciences. This multidisciplinary methodology enables a thorough examination of political processes, including the intricate interplay of social, economic, and environmental elements. Political science encompasses many sub-branches, including political theory, political ecology, and political economics. These sub-branches are characterized by their interdisciplinary nature, as they draw upon information and methodology from a range of social and scientific disciplines. This multidisciplinary method enhances the examination of political events by taking into account the interactions of social, economic, and environmental aspects in a comprehensive way. To summarize, the sub-disciplines of political science, such as political theory, political ecology, and political

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economics, are fundamentally multidisciplinary studies that integrate knowledge and approaches from many social and scientific sciences.

Interdisciplinary Approaches to Political Science

Political science connects with other fields, including economics, geography, ethnography, ecology, and conservation biology. By including social, economic, and environmental variables, interdisciplinary methods enrich the understanding of political processes. This multidisciplinary approach enables a more complete and all-encompassing examination of political events, including the many aspects of human behavior, institutions, and power relations. Political science has evident interconnections and intersections with several other disciplines, notably economics, geography, anthropology, psychology, sociology, and ecology. Political science utilizes ideas and approaches from other disciplines to get a comprehensive knowledge of the intricate nature of political processes and the interplay between people, communities, and surroundings. In essence, the many subdivisions of political science, such as political theory, political ecology, and political economics, are essentially multidisciplinary domains that use knowledge and approaches from other social and scientific disciplines. Political ecology exemplifies an interdisciplinary approach within political science, integrating information from social sciences such as political economics with ideas from natural sciences like ecology (Tevzadze & Kikvidze, 2016). This multidisciplinary method enhances the examination of political events by taking into account the interaction of social, economic, and environmental aspects.

Relations with Other Sciences

Political science has robust interconnections and intersections with several other disciplines, notably economics, geography, anthropology, psychology, sociology, and ecology. These fields of study provide significant perspectives and approaches that improve the analysis of political issues. Political science may evaluate governance systems, market failures, and regulatory ideas by integrating economic theories. Geography enhances the field of political science by

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analyzing the geographical aspects of political occurrences, such as territorial boundaries, allocation of resources, and the influence of geography on political strife. Anthropology offers insights into the cultural and social influences that mold political behavior and institutions. Psychology provides insights into the processes of decision-making at both individual and collective levels, as well as the psychological elements that impact political behavior and views. Sociology investigates the overarching social frameworks and mechanisms that influence political occurrences, including socioeconomic disparities, social movements, and the function of establishments in society. Ecology provides insights into the interactions between people and their natural environment, emphasizing the environmental aspects that impact political decision-making and policy results. In general, political science gains advantages from its interdisciplinary approach and cooperation with other scientific disciplines since it enables a more thorough comprehension of political processes. Furthermore, multidisciplinary cooperation extends beyond the confines of political science only. Various other subjects, including environmental science, international relations, public health, and communication studies, also participate in interdisciplinary study alongside political science. This collaboration aims to investigate intricate matters that arise at the convergence of politics and their respective domains. The need of precise weather predictions in today's dynamic environment cannot be overemphasized. Political science establishes connections with other scientific disciplines via different means and gains advantages from interdisciplinary partnerships. Political science utilizes ideas and approaches from other disciplines, including economics, geography, anthropology, psychology, sociology, and ecology, to enhance its knowledge of political processes and generate more informed assessments and forecasts. Political scientists may study governance systems, market failures, and regulatory ideas by adding economic theories. Furthermore, geography, as an interdisciplinary field, enhances political science by analyzing the spatial aspects of political processes, including territorial boundaries, allocation of resources, and the geopolitical impact of various locations (Ramadhyas et al., 2020). In addition, anthropology gives essential perspectives on the cultural and social determinants that influence political behavior and views, while psychology provides insights into the human cognitive processes and motives that underlie political attitudes and decision-making. In general, political science gains advantages by collaborating with other disciplines and areas, which enables a more thorough comprehension of political events. Furthermore, it improves

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the credibility and relevance of research results since many viewpoints and approaches may provide supplementary views and evidence. Political science is an interdisciplinary discipline that derives advantages from cooperation with diverse sciences such as economics, geography, anthropology, psychology, sociology, and ecology. Interdisciplinary partnerships provide a holistic understanding of political processes by integrating perspectives and approaches from several disciplines, enabling more informed analyses and forecasts. The need of precise weather predictions in today's dynamic environment cannot be overemphasized. The need of precise weather predictions in today's dynamic environment cannot be overemphasized. The need of precise weather predictions in today's dynamic environment cannot be overemphasized. The importance of precise multidisciplinary interactions cannot be exaggerated in the current fast-paced global environment. The importance of precise multidisciplinary partnerships cannot be exaggerated in the fast-paced modern environment. Political science is an intrinsically interdisciplinary discipline that gains advantages from cooperation with other disciplines and areas, including economics, geography, anthropology, psychology, sociology, and ecology. These partnerships provide a holistic understanding of political events by integrating perspectives and approaches from several disciplines, enabling more informed analyses and forecasts. The need of precise multidisciplinary partnerships in political science cannot be emphasized enough in the current dynamic global landscape. The importance of precise multidisciplinary cooperation in political science cannot be exaggerated in the current era of fast change. The importance of precise multidisciplinary partnerships in political science cannot be exaggerated in the current dynamic global landscape. Political science is an interdisciplinary study that derives advantages from cooperation with other sciences, including economics, geography, anthropology, psychology, sociology, and ecology. These partnerships provide a holistic understanding of political events by integrating perspectives and approaches from several disciplines, enabling more informed analyses and forecasts. Political science is an interdisciplinary discipline that thrives on cooperation with other sciences and areas, including economics, geography, anthropology, psychology, sociology, and ecology. These multidisciplinary partnerships in political science provide a comprehensive and sophisticated approach to researching and comprehending political behavior, processes, and phenomena in the intricate and linked world of today. The importance of precise multidisciplinary partnerships in political science cannot be exaggerated in today's fast-paced environment. Political science

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is a subject that naturally involves several disciplines and gains advantages from working together with numerous other sciences and areas. These partnerships provide a holistic understanding of political events by integrating perspectives and approaches from several disciplines, enabling more informed analyses and forecasts. The importance of precise multidisciplinary partnerships in political science cannot be exaggerated in the current dynamic global landscape. The need of precise multidisciplinary partnerships in political science cannot be emphasized enough in the current dynamic global landscape. Political science, being an interdisciplinary domain, depends on cooperation with other disciplines and areas to acquire a more thorough comprehension of political processes and formulate informed analyses and forecasts. Political science incorporates knowledge from several disciplines like geography, anthropology, political economy, ecology, conservation biology, economics, psychology, and sociology.

Political Science and its Interdisciplinary Relations

Political science, being an interdisciplinary domain, depends on cooperation with other disciplines and areas to acquire a more thorough comprehension of political processes and provide well-informed analyses and forecasts. These relationships facilitate the integration of knowledge and approaches from other disciplines, including economics, geography, anthropology, psychology, sociology, and ecology. Political science employs a range of interdisciplinary fields, including geography, anthropology, political economics, ecology, and conservation biology, to investigate and examine political behavior, systems, and phenomena using various techniques and research tools. In addition, the interdisciplinary aspect of political science is enhanced by the inclusion of political ecology and conservation and development studies, which need the integration of information from both social and natural sciences (Tevzadze & Kikvidze, 2016). The multidisciplinary aspect of political science is essential in the contemporary dynamic environment since precise analyses and forecasts need a complete comprehension of political occurrences. Political science, being an interdisciplinary domain, encompasses not only the study of politics but also entails cooperation with several other disciplines and areas. Political science benefits from interdisciplinary collaborations, which

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allow it to integrate perspectives and approaches from various fields, including economics, geography, anthropology, psychology, sociology, and conservation biology. This integration strengthens its capacity to examine and analyze political behavior, systems, and phenomena. Political science may include several techniques and research procedures, including in-depth interviews, sociological and ecological surveys, participant observation, and the use of geospatial and remote sensing technologies, via collaboration with other disciplines. Political scientists may analyze the intricate interplay between social and ecological elements that impact political behavior and systems using this multidisciplinary approach. Political science integrates knowledge and techniques from diverse disciplines such as geography, anthropology, political economy, psychology, sociology, and ecology. This interdisciplinary approach enables a thorough comprehension of political phenomena and facilitates informed analysis and predictions.

The interdisciplinary nature of political science is crucial in today's rapidly changing world as accurate analyses and predictions require a comprehensive understanding of political phenomena.

Political science is intrinsically multidisciplinary, using information from other social and scientific disciplines to examine and understand political behavior, institutions, and events. Political scientists may analyze the intricate interplay between social and ecological elements that shape politics using this multidisciplinary approach. Political science is not the only discipline that is multidisciplinary. Other subjects, such as political ecology and conservation and development studies, also seek to integrate information from both social and natural sciences. Political science expands beyond its conventional confines by engaging in interdisciplinary partnerships, integrating perspectives and approaches from other fields such as economics, geography, anthropology, psychology, sociology, and conservation biology. Through this approach, political science may provide a more thorough comprehension of political processes and conduct precise analyses and forecasts in the dynamic contemporary world. Political science is an interdisciplinary discipline that works along with many social and scientific sciences to examine and evaluate political behavior and processes. Geography, being

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a multidisciplinary field, is essential for comprehending political behavior in geographical political systems (Ramadhyas et al., 2020). Geography offers the geographical framework and examination required to comprehend the allocation of political authority, resources, and conduct. Furthermore, it should be noted that political theory, a topic within the broader discipline of political science, does not exhibit a higher degree of interdisciplinarity compared to the field as a whole (Corbett, 2011). It utilizes knowledge and techniques from several fields, including as economics, sociology, psychology, geography, and other related areas. This multidisciplinary approach enables a more holistic comprehension of political occurrences, since it considers not only social variables, but also the environmental and ecological components that mold and impact political behavior. In summary, political science is a highly multidisciplinary discipline that incorporates information and approaches from several social sciences such as economics, sociology, psychology, and anthropology, as well as natural sciences like geography, ecology, and conservation biology. The need of precise and thorough political analysis in today's dynamic environment cannot be emphasized enough. Political science is an interdisciplinary discipline that works along with many social and scientific sciences to examine and evaluate political behavior and processes. Political science is a multidisciplinary field that collaborates and integrates with various branches of social sciences, including anthropology, sociology, psychology, economics, and geography. It also intersects with interdisciplinary fields such as political ecology and conservation and development studies.

Interdisciplinarity in Political Science and its Relations with Other Sciences

Interdisciplinarity in political science is the cooperative and amalgamation of several social and scientific sciences to examine and scrutinize political behavior and institutions. This approach acknowledges that a comprehensive understanding of politics cannot be achieved by only studying one subject, but instead necessitates the incorporation of concepts and approaches from other areas. The multidisciplinary method heavily relies on geography, since it offers the physical context and analysis required to comprehend the distribution of political power, resources, and election processes. Political science also connects with other disciplines,

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including economics, sociology, psychology, and anthropology. These fields of study enhance our knowledge of political phenomena by analyzing the sociological, economic, psychological, and cultural influences that determine political conduct. Furthermore, political science incorporates knowledge and approaches from natural disciplines such as ecology and conservation biology. The field of political ecology investigates the connections between human societies and their ecosystems, analyzing the influence of political and economic systems on ecological processes (Tevzadze & Kikvidze, 2016). In addition, political science extends beyond cooperation with particular disciplines and encompasses transdisciplinary and applied subjects such as political ecology and conservation and development studies. Political science is an interdisciplinary study that combines knowledge and methods from many social and natural sciences. It aims to provide a thorough understanding of political behavior and systems within their wider social and environmental settings. To summarize, political science is a fundamentally interdisciplinary discipline that works along with other social disciplines, including anthropology, sociology, psychology, and economics. Additionally, it incorporates knowledge derived from natural disciplines such as ecology and geography to provide a thorough comprehension of political behavior and systems. This multidisciplinary approach acknowledges the intricacy of political occurrences and aims to cultivate a comprehensive comprehension by incorporating various viewpoints and approaches. Political science is an interdisciplinary discipline that works along with social sciences including anthropology, sociology, psychology, and economics. Furthermore, it incorporates knowledge derived from natural disciplines such as ecology and geography to provide a thorough comprehension of political behavior and systems. This interdisciplinary approach recognizes the intricate and interrelated nature of political issues, acknowledging that a thorough comprehension requires ideas and approaches from other disciplines. To summarize, political science is a fundamentally interdisciplinary discipline that works along with a range of social disciplines, including anthropology, sociology, psychology, and economics. Furthermore, it incorporates knowledge and techniques derived from natural sciences such as ecology and geography, while adopting interdisciplinary methods such as political ecology (as outlined in the IUCN SSC recommendations on human-wildlife conflict and cohabitation, 2023). These multidisciplinary methods provide a thorough comprehension of political behavior and systems, including the social, economic, and ecological aspects that influence political processes. Political science is

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an interdisciplinary study that works along with other social sciences and incorporates knowledge from natural sciences, such ecology and geography, to provide a thorough comprehension of political behavior and systems. This interdisciplinary approach acknowledges the interdependence of political events with social, economic, and environmental aspects and seeks to cultivate a complete understanding by merging concepts and approaches from several disciplines. Political science is an interdisciplinary discipline that works along with other social sciences and incorporates knowledge from natural sciences, such ecology and geography, to provide a full comprehension of political behavior and systems. By incorporating many disciplines, this method enables a more intricate examination of political events, taking into account the societal, economic, and environmental influences that mold political processes. Political science is an interdisciplinary discipline that works along with other social sciences, including anthropology, sociology, psychology, and economics. Political science integrates knowledge and techniques from disciplines such as ecology and geography to improve the understanding of political behavior and processes. Political science is an interdisciplinary study that works along with other social sciences and incorporates knowledge from natural sciences to provide a thorough comprehension of political behavior and processes. Political science is an interdisciplinary discipline that works along with other social sciences, including anthropology, sociology, psychology, and economics. Political science integrates knowledge and approaches from disciplines such as ecology and geography to improve understanding of political behavior and systems. Political science is an interdisciplinary discipline that works along with social sciences including anthropology, sociology, psychology, and economics. Political science utilizes multidisciplinary cooperation to integrate concepts and approaches from disciplines such as ecology and geography, so enriching the understanding of political behavior and systems. Political science is an interdisciplinary study that works with different social sciences and incorporates knowledge from natural sciences, such ecology and geography, to provide a full comprehension of political behavior and systems. To summarize, political science is a fundamentally interdisciplinary discipline that works along with a range of social disciplines, including anthropology, sociology, psychology, and economics. Political science utilizes multidisciplinary cooperation to integrate concepts and approaches from disciplines such as ecology and geography, so enriching the understanding of political behavior and systems. Political science is an interdisciplinary discipline that works along with other social

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sciences, including anthropology, sociology, psychology, and economics. Political science utilizes multidisciplinary cooperation to integrate concepts and approaches from disciplines such as ecology and geography, so enriching the understanding of political behavior and systems. Political science is an interdisciplinary study that works with different social sciences and incorporates knowledge from natural sciences, such as ecology and geography, to provide a full comprehension of political behavior and systems. Political science is an interdisciplinary discipline that works along with social sciences including anthropology, sociology, psychology, and economics. Interdisciplinary partnerships enhance political science by integrating multiple viewpoints and approaches, enabling a full comprehension of political behavior and systems. Political science is an interdisciplinary study that works closely with other social sciences, including anthropology, sociology, psychology, and economics. Political science is an interdisciplinary discipline that works along with social sciences including anthropology, sociology, psychology, and economics. Political science utilizes multidisciplinary cooperation to integrate concepts and approaches from disciplines such as ecology and geography, so enriching the understanding of political behavior and systems. Political science is a discipline that naturally combines knowledge and methods from several social and scientific sciences. Political science is an interdisciplinary study that incorporates knowledge and methods from several social and natural sciences, such as geography, ethnography, political economics, ecology, and conservation biology. Political science may achieve a complete knowledge of political behavior and systems by embracing multiple viewpoints and approaches via multidisciplinary cooperation. Political science is a subject that combines knowledge and methods from several social and natural sciences, such as geography, ethnography, political economics, ecology, and conservation biology. Political science incorporates information and methodology from other social disciplines, including anthropology, sociology, psychology, and economics, via interdisciplinary cooperation. Additionally, it employs methodologies and research instruments derived from geography, ethnography, political economics, ecology, and conservation biology. To summarize, political science is a fundamentally interdisciplinary discipline that works along with a range of social disciplines, including anthropology, sociology, psychology, and economics. Political science may provide a thorough and all-encompassing comprehension of political behavior and systems by considering the intricate interplay of social, economic, and environmental aspects. Political science is an

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interdisciplinary discipline that works along with social sciences including anthropology, sociology, psychology, and economics.

Conclusion

Political science may enhance its knowledge of political behavior and systems by integrating concepts and approaches from disciplines like ecology and geography. Political science is a subject that combines knowledge and methods from several social and natural sciences, such as geography, anthropology, political economics, psychology, and sociology (Corbett, 2011). Political science may provide a thorough comprehension of political behavior and systems by integrating many viewpoints and approaches via multidisciplinary cooperation. To summarize, political science is a fundamentally interdisciplinary discipline that works along with a range of social disciplines, including anthropology, sociology, psychology, and economics. By doing so, it may provide a thorough understanding of political behavior and systems, considering the intricate interplay of social, economic, and environmental aspects. Political science is an interdisciplinary field that integrates knowledge and methods from several social and natural disciplines, including anthropology, sociology, psychology, economics, geography, political economy, ecology, and conservation biology. Political science achieves a comprehensive comprehension of political behavior and systems by embracing multidisciplinary cooperation and taking into account the interdependence of social, economic, and environmental aspects. Political science is an interdisciplinary field that incorporates concepts and approaches from many social sciences, including anthropology, sociology, psychology, and economics, as well as natural sciences such as ecology and geography. By engaging in multidisciplinary partnerships, political science may provide a thorough understanding of political behavior and systems, including the intricate interplay of social, economic, and environmental aspects. Political science is an interdisciplinary discipline that incorporates knowledge and methods from several social and natural sciences, such as anthropology, sociology, psychology, economics, geography, political economy, ecology, and conservation biology. Political science may achieve a complete knowledge of political behavior and systems by adopting

multidisciplinary partnerships that take into account the interconnectivity of social, economic, and environmental elements.

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